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Towards Transformation through Social Responsibility: Assessing Partnership in Education

Abstract: Social responsibility transforms lives through social inclusions. Social inclusion is initiated in different foundations to modify behaviour and transform social lives. This transformation can be highly visible within the deprived groups, who are aloof from the quality and sophisticated modern technologies. One of the transformations through Institutional Social Responsibility (ISR) is partnering in education. Within this educational partnering for social inclusion, St. Xavier's College (SXC) as a host organization has initiated a programme for the deprived group who are distant from modern facilities. The foundational programme for social educational partnering is the Partnership in Education (PiE). The PiE programme is a multi-dimensional educative project that is designed for the benefit of students. This study explored the transformation of students in behaviour, personality, academics, and overall development, and enhancement of ability through becoming socially responsible further leading to quality educational lives. Within the qualitative research design, the interview was applied. Data triangulation was used for analysis. The respondents for this study were PiE supervisor, counselor, volunteers, coordinators, and students. Altogether, interviews were conducted with eight respondents. The findings suggest that PiE can transform lives of the underprivileged students. The introduction of modern technologies to support quality education during the PiE has enabled the students to develop additional knowledge through the use and applicability of digitalization in education. PiE students' level of confidence has positive growth- reflecting their personality change. It has been found that students' behavioural transformation is visible in PiE. The volunteers who support the PiE programme have been developing their personalities through self-confidence and leadership skills. PiE has contributed towards social transformations by becoming institutionally responsible for the holistic development of students. The PiE programme is gaining its ground to benefit deprived students through this academic collaboration. Learning a new and skillful lesson from PiE has encouraged the students to boost their interest in particular subject areas. The benefits from the PiE are not limited alone to traditional education. The findings suggest that partnership between host organizations and the collaborating schools can strengthen the transformation growth in students who are deprived of modern and quality educational activities.

Keywords: Social responsibility, partnership in education, underprivileged, social inclusion, transformation, academic, educational lives

Introduction

Social responsibility is an essential element towards contributions to social welfare in which individuals are morally obliged to serve society. Social responsibility and accountability are civic responsibilities and duties an organization has towards its society and community people. Educational organizations/institutes need moral responsibility to perform their social and civic responsibility through educating citizens. Colby et al., (2003) claim that moral duty and socio-civic responsibility must be intertwined.

Transformation and educating citizens have become effective with collaboration and partnership in education. According to Snow (2011), clever partnerships are collaborations linking the assets and tasks of institutions with community property and interests for effective lengthy-term effect. UNESCO relies on a wide variety of alliances and partnerships to pursue its mission and implement its programs. Partnering with UNESCO is a commitment to the highest standards of fairness, impartiality, accountability, and excellence (UNESCO, 2023).

Partnership in education through international collaboration has been felt necessary to enhance the capability of educational lives within needy people. This generates a sense of socio-civic responsibility while it promotes educating citizens with modern educational methods. Rajbhandari (2018) states educational lives can be obtained by ‘obstinate actions-oriented behaviour’ which is acquired through content-based, process-based learning and spawning critical reflexivity of learned phenomena into practical actions. This obstinate actions-oriented behaviour is oriented in two spheres 1) science obstinate action and 2) an art-obstinate action, which is the method (science obstinate action) and why and how method (art-obstinate action) of teaching. While attempts are made to promote educational lives, the art of obstinate action orientation is necessary, which brings about the essence of the modern educational method towards transforming students through enhancing educational lives by going beyond the traditional educational system.

Towards making partnership in education effective through socio-civic responsibility, St. Xavier’s College has initiated Partnership in Education (PiE) to enhance the quality of educational lives of underprivileged students.

The World Bank (2013) defines social inclusion as the process of bettering the terms for individuals and groups to participate in society or more specifically the process of enhancing the capacity, opportunity, and nobility of people, who are underprivileged based on their identity, to engage in society. PiE at St. Xavier’s College includes the underprivileged children of the ambient communities to ensure their holistic development through the introduction of quality education and all-around facilities. PiE is working towards bringing about positive transformation in children’s academics, morals, and personality.

Partnering in education is a social cause of becoming accountable to the societal community. Collaboration in education can bring about changes in behavioural patterns and growth in academics by enhancing the quality of educational lives. The expectancy of educational activities in recent times is changing its course from a traditional to a modern educational system. Underprivileged students coming from poor families are

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often deprived of these changes surrounding the modern educational system. To raise the quality of educational lives for underprivileged students, partnership in education can become a necessity for the poor community. Academic collaboration has been felt essential for those who are deprived of modern educational facilities. This can be fulfilled by partnering in education where deprived groups can have access to modern education.

The paper aims to study the contributions of PiE through becoming socially responsible towards the deprived community students with the support of the host organization and its members. This study focused on learning about the workings of PiE and the perspectives of the students and staff to assess the impacts PiE poses in the improvement of the educational lives of students. This study explored the transformation of students in terms of their personality development through bringing about changes in behaviour, enhanced ability, and academic growth ensuring quality educational lives. This is explored with the following research questions.

Research questions

1. How has PiE been able to transform the growth and development of students? (Academic growth)
2. How is PiE supporting in enhancing the quality of educational lives of the students?
3. How is PiE widening social responsibility parameters?

Literature Review

Volunteerism and Social Responsibility

Volunteerism offers an opportunity to connect and network with people which widens the area of one's exposure to knowledge and assets. Few social organizations offer the opportunity to build trusting intergenerational relationships and connect young people to useful sources of information, resources, and opportunities (King and Roeser, 2009). Youth are the ones who often engage in several pursuits willingly to enhance their skills, knowledge, and potential to gain academic credentials for higher studies and career prospects. Most of today's youth are actively involved in volunteering as a form of social service around various realms that concern their interests and expertise while social organizations are unhesitatingly encouraging them to join as it benefits them and their purpose too. This depicts that both the youth and social organizations profited through the act of volunteering.

The present and the future of society are the students hence educational institutions need to realize their roles in shaping the students' values and mindsets. To establish students as good citizens the institution itself must be a good citizen to enhance and rebuild bonds of trust in the society; i.e., "social capital" and to use the neutrality of the campus to provide a safe platform where different opinions and advocacy for every notion and perspective can be acknowledged liberally and constructively and where people with similar goals can come together and work in conjunction (Sihem, 2013). More students need to engage in volunteering so that they can learn more about their societies and actively participate in the change-making process.

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Access to Inclusive Quality Education for Underprivileged

Most of the slum school teachers tend to avoid school, not because they are lazy or uninterested but because they are unable to ignore the immense problems that come along. This is why many school and college administrators are prioritizing vocational training for slum schools (Ornstein, 1968), however, can local competence centers play an essential role in fighting poverty through professional qualifications? (Wallenborn, 2009). Wallenborn (2009) further emphasized that vocational training helps promote social balance and sustainable monetary and social advancement. Currently, many schools and colleges interview applicants and provide them with a brief knowledge of the school atmosphere with needed training in the presence of other educators before hiring them. This helps to ensure that the new teacher is well-informed about the school environment, curriculum, rules, regulations, and the students. However, concerning the government schools and colleges, many still lack these facilities which has created an educational gap in the government schools.

There is no public education system in the world that possesses equal educational access to all. Socio-economic background, motivation, policies or laws et cetera are a few of the many aspects that dictate distinctions among students in compulsory school systems (Bădescu and Pop, 2012). Nevertheless, in the present scenario, educational institutions have introduced digital learning, the use of ICTs in classrooms, scholarships for needy students based on certain criteria, free education policy for primary-level students, et cetera. In addition to that, developing an inclusive education system is crucial which involves the use of special technologies for the differently abled ones, unique pedagogical styles, knowledge and training regarding the use of devices in the classroom, a syllabus covering a wide range of topics, and so on.

Accessing Partnership in Education Internationally

As two fundamental parts of society, universities and industry each play an important role in the development and progress of society. Academia and industry have worked together for more than a century, but the rise of the global knowledge-based economy has increased the need for strategic partnerships beyond the traditional pattern of individual projects. Bold and visionary partnerships between industry and academia can aid in enhancing innovation and deliver solutions to pressing societal challenges (Zha, Guangfen, and Zhong, 2016). Prioritizing the need for partnership in the field of education, many international industries, universities, and projects have come together to work for quality education policy formation and implementation in schools and colleges.

As part of its internationalization agenda, a university develops various international relations and cooperation agreements with foreign partners to expand and strengthen its core undertakings of teaching, research, and knowledge transfer (Woodfield and Middlehurst, 2009). The partnership-building procedure comprehends establishing rapport with several institutions or organizations that even undergo certain legal proceedings. They aid in providing inclusive education to underprivileged students through educational access and services required for their all-round development. Furthermore, the partnerships are often profit-centered which presents them as unreliable in the bigger picture, this is because selfless social services are generally anticipated from larger institutions by the public.

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Accessing Partnership in Education Nationally

As defined by Stăiculescu, Richițeanu-Năstase, and Dobra (2015), from a legal point of view, a partnership is defined as a legal contract in which the partners jointly determine the general purpose, the obligations of the partners and the conditions under which the partnership relationship is formed. In the context of Nepal, partnerships usually happen through international funding. Nepal is considered a late initiator of development in South Asia. Only in the early 1950s did the country open up to the outside world and planned development efforts, and the influx of aid began almost simultaneously. Over time, foreign aid has proven to be a powerful tool contributing to significant improvements in a country's socio-economic development (Ministry of Finance, 2002).

An exemplary partnership in the education sector in Nepal was the World Federation of the Deaf's (WFD) policies implemented for the development of inclusive education for deaf learners. The WFD develops its objectives by the principles and goals of the United Nations (UN) Charter, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, including the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, and other general laws and recommendations of the United Nations and its specialized agencies. It is working towards the goal of equal opportunity and full participation of deaf people in all countries (WFD, 2016). This was a great step in establishing an inclusive education system in the country that can benefit those in need. Similarly, Durbar High School and NGOs are active participants in educational partnerships to strengthen inclusive education for deprived students. (Rajbhandari, 2011).

Transforming Education through Digitalization and Technology

The process of digitizing education has been going on for a long time. However, between the temporary restrictions on communication related to Covid-19 and the widespread shift to fully remote forms of interaction between all participants in the educational process, there has been a surge in interest. Digitization is impacting education at all levels, directly impacting the activities of students, teachers, administrators, or stakeholders (Petrușevich, 2020). At the present moment, digital technologies such as computers, laptops, TVs, mobile phones, projectors, and so on are used in school administration to enhance the teaching and learning environment. A survey conducted by Islam and Jahan (2018), among primary and secondary level students in Bangladesh to assess the impacts of digitalization in the education system of schools, reported that 95.4% of students were happy with the use of digital devices in the classroom as it helped them to grasp the content matter more effectively.

Students can learn in an effective way where learning goes beyond the typical way of memorizing concepts. Integration of digital technologies emphasizes the need to make the students understand the content matter through audio, visuals, gamification, and so on. Concerning Nepal, the initiatives on the development of ICT in education policy, its introduction into curricula, the establishment of computer labs in rural primary schools, and the involvement of NGOs in ICT training for teachers have been instrumental in translating traditional teaching methods into modern teaching and learning strategies. However, there exists a gap between those aspirations and reality, hence to implement this policy, the government must not limit itself to merely developing strategies to equip all schools in the country and train teachers to use available digital

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technologies, but also assess relevant socio-economic and physical challenges that come along (Maski Rana, 2018).

Enhancement of Quality Education through Extra-Curricular Activities

It has long been known that after-school activities contribute in many ways not only to improving the social skills of students but also to enhancing their school experience. In addition to creating school culture and fostering school spirit, extracurricular activities are associated with improved student performance, the discovery of responsibilities, the discovery of skills and interests, and self-discipline and leadership skills (Adeyemo, 2010). These include sports, events, clubs, performances, exhibitions of creative ideas, designing, et cetera. However, the challenge lies in practice, as per a study conducted by Khan and Iqbal (2014), extracurricular activities are not being practiced in the Pakistani school system as parents believed that students' capabilities depended upon their academic grades rather than other skills or abilities. The stereotype exists in several other developing nations including Nepal, parents consider extracurricular activities a waste of time and this leads to the feeling of discouragement among the students.

Parents' educational expectations influence school performance directly through the desired goals and behaviours they define for their children, and indirectly through performance-enhancing behaviours related to parental educational expectations. Examples of such behaviour at home include parental interest and involvement in children's learning and school activities and the extent to which parents act as role models for their children's learning and achievement. In particular, parental ambitions and expectations enhance home learning, academic confidence and support, and parent-child educational conversations are positive indicators of motivation (Seginer, 1983; Boonk, Gijsselaers, Ritzen and Brand-Gruwel, 2022). Here, school counselors can play an important role. According to Wilson (2009), school counselors could assist in eliminating the barriers to students' participation and encourage involvement in their best interests. They or the teachers can also work with the parents and educate them about the benefits of children's engagement in extra activities while persuading them to allow their children to enjoy their hobbies and interests.

Methodology

The research area for this study was at St. Xavier's College at Loyola Campus. This research is qualitatively designed. A case study was conducted. An interview tool was applied. The respondents for this study included eight respondents who were interviewed and among these respondents, there were three employees (supervisor, coordinator, and counselor), one former trainee and one former volunteer, and three students who were involved with the PiE programme. Research questions for the interview were prepared which were asked of the respondents. The interview was conducted on a one-on-one basis with individual respondents while also maintaining ethical considerations. Data was tape-recorded which was translated and transcribed for validation purposes. Data triangulation was used for data analysis. These data were triangulated within the respondent's answers using the coding techniques for further analysis. For the accuracy and credibility of the interview questions, a pilot test was applied before the data collection and analysis.

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Findings and discussions

It is presumed that education is the only means that offers ways towards development. Moreover, educational activities are the determinant factor that enhances the standard of student growth holistically. Education and educational activities are the key ingredients that play a pivotal role in the developmental aspects of educational lives. Education enhances the ways to transformation, growth, quality, and behavioural changes, through knowledge which is also the social responsibility of an organization for the betterment of students and educational organizations.

Many educational organizations are inclined towards rendering intellectual and educative services to many. However, educational activities for example collaboration and partnering in education and educational activities are a growing concern for many organizations in recent days. Partnering in education is a major activity that can tend to shape the future. Partnership in education is essential rather than a desirable element that any organization requires for the growth and development within the educational community. This study focuses on the partnership in education and highlights the key components that it is contributing towards bringing about the growth and development, quality, personality, changes in behaviours, transformation, and social responsibility of all towards the betterment of the entire nation altogether.

So far, St. Xavier's College has taken the initiative towards becoming socially responsible while driving the partnership in education with multiple government schools. This initiation has taken many years and the results of this are reflected in the transformation of students to obtain the quality in education. While initiating a partnership in education for the betterment of students of government/public schools, the partnership in education is also focused on the development of students' personalities and changes in behaviours along with the growth in academics.

Transformation through educational partnering

Transformation is an imminent factor for every student while at school. While it is observed that transformation can take a slow pace but with partnership in education the pace can be accelerated. In such circumstances, the program of partnership in education at St. Xavier's College has taken its accelerating pace toward the transformation of students through implementing educative activities that were far to obtain from other means. This is generally due to the lack of adequate infrastructure at the public schools. The disadvantages of the public schools are generally fulfilled by the partnership in educational activities with other equipped institutes/organizations. Moreover, the educational activities that are delivered by the host organization in partnership with education can have multiple benefits to the students and one of the major benefits can be transformation. This transformation can be generated through academic means, activities, socialization, technologies, modern teaching methods, and so forth.

Without transformation, partnering in education can have less meaning and thus offer fewer benefits to the participants. Partnership in Education (PiE) for the transformation of students in entire academic activities is the key objective that a host institute/organization must concentrate on while taking up the educational partnership program as a social responsibility. While such initiatives are limited and a few organizations

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offer to act as host organizations, both academic and other educative activities need to be developed to focus on transforming the lives of every student. Respondent 8 mentions the initiation of partnership in an education programme that benefits the student participants through educative activities.

“The PiE classes are run in the mornings; the volunteers and trainees take care of the classes. We focus on the subjects as well as other activities which help students grow academically where they perform better in their academics and also get the opportunity to participate in several outdoor and indoor activities, therefore, enhancing their innate talents”

Respondent 1 supports this by stating;

“PiE classes are usually run every Sunday-Friday where Sunday-Thursday academic classes are conducted, during these days we teach the students different academic subjects. Speaking of benefits, the students receive in PiE, the questions students find difficult to solve at home, they get to learn about in PiE as our volunteers teach them every individual subject. The concepts students learn in school are repeated in PiE hence they revise and learn better”.

While PiE has immense contributions towards shaping the students’ lives through academic transformation, it is equally necessary to bring about transformation through other means of educative activities. About this, respondent 4 (PiE student) mentions;

“Every Friday we have moral classes where we watch stories and documentaries on TV and at the end the teachers ask us to share a review on it. They also teach us moral lessons, good behaviours, and habits. Then, a volunteer used to come, he was very good at teaching. While studying under his guidance we built a very good relationship. PiE is a St. Xavier’s organization hence PiE students are often looked upon as academically good students”.

In most cases, the host organization faces quite a bit of behavioural problems from the PiE participants. This is the major difficulty for a host organization, while the change of behaviour and transforming the students’ lives can become an important aspect to focus, on while at the initial stage of initiating the PiE programme. Rajbhandari (2021) states that an individual’s behaviours are directly connected with their level of attitude within the attitudinal and behavioural commitment to whether to change or not. Multiple micro attributes relate to an individual’s commitment level. These micro attributes shape the individual’s behavioural pattern triggering towards increase or decrease of the individual’s Open-Source Understanding (OSU) and Close Source Understanding (CSU), which also determines to shape the individual’s personality. Rajbhandari (2021) further claims that at a certain stage, there will be a personality crisis which is the state of Collision of Ignorance (COI) and Collision of Acceptance (COA). These states of COI and COA in an individual instigate change in the behavioural pattern.

Regarding the individual behavioural pattern of PiE participants, respondent 8 stating

“There have been many students in PiE who have had serious issues concerning their behaviour and academics but over the years we have seen a lot of changes in them. We transform them into better human beings, many of them have gone to study in reputed colleges and they have become responsible towards others as well”

Supporting this view, respondent 7 addresses;

“Sometimes I feel that students just want the benefit, some students study but some just come for nothing. They don’t want to study and expect other benefits like engagement in extra activities and receiving gifts on occasion.”

Bringing about behavioural changes is an indispensable factor in PiE, and this change is an important concern for the PiE host. Through PiE, it has been found that students’ behavioural transformation is visible, although it is a time-consuming process, the environmental forces can have a driving initiative to bring about this transformation within students. Respondent 3 (PiE student) speaks of the transformation process by stating;

“PiE teaches us how to behave in society, improve academic performance, and respect everyone including friends and families. There are no specific classes for it but the teachers teach us such things in between the classes”.

Respondent 2 (PiE student) supports this view by mentioning;

“PiE teaches us how to talk and behave with others...while presenting motivational videos, they teach us many good values”.

In the same line, respondent 4 mentions;

“If there was no PiE, we would have to pay for other tuition classes to study. Hence, the PiE program benefits us as it is free of charge. My mommy baba always tell me to join PiE class each day as it, according to them, develops a habit of waking up early and working hard”.

Partnering in education by the host organization has a daunting task to perform while taking responsibility as well as becoming accountable to students by transforming their lives through education and educative activities. Although hosting PiE is taken as a simple responsibility by the host organization, a pivotal concern about initiating the PiE programme is its accountability to transform the lives of unprivileged and underprivileged students. The PiE programme has taken its hype to such an extent that many have benefited from this sort of academic collaboration.

Academic growth and development of students

Academic collaboration with the PiE programme is always predetermined to bring about academic growth and development in students who are participating as PiE members representing different schools. It is not necessary that PiE collaboration can guarantee the highest level of academic growth and develop the academic standard. Nevertheless, with the essence of quality in education that the students were deprived of the possibility of receiving it through the PiE can be a generous offer provided by the hosting organization/institutes, which enables the students to boost their academic standard.

Within academic growth, students can enhance their learning capability while they are with the other institutes as PiE members. In such cases, the academic growth of students can be further enhanced by offering them quality education that they were deprived of at their home institute. Moreover, additional support is received as tutoring to learn further with the host institute teachers. This additional support from the host institute can be very helpful to the students craving academic help from others. About this respondent 4 (student) says;

“Some might have cousins, brothers, and sisters in their homes it’s easy for them but those who don’t, need a supporter. What happens when we come to PiE is, that the things we don’t know and are confused about are taught by the teachers who act like our supporters. We also feel comfortable asking questions as the teachers here treat us like brothers and sisters hence it’s easier to learn from them. It can’t be compared to the school because PiE is an organization. Speaking of how it’s different from schools, in schools we have different timings and we have particular subjects scheduled whereas in PiE we get to ask everything we don’t know at any time we want”.

Moreover, joining as a PiE member also benefits the students as they learn in a new educational realm. Educational activities are not only limited to academic growth alone but learning new and skillful lessons from PiE can encourage the students to boost their interest in particular subject areas. In this regard, respondent 3 (student) says;

“Personally, my ECAs and academics have improved since joining PiE. The school mostly focuses on academics and I wanted to learn new stuff. We get a lot of opportunities in PiE. I am interested in art and my art skills have improved a lot.”

Most PiE students also claim that their academic standard has improved with the help that they have received since joining the PiE programme. Moreover, the free learning platform with the PiE programme has additional benefits for the students in their academic progress. In connection to this, respondent 2 (student) mentions;

“Talking about the benefit we receive in PiE, it is free classes, not everyone can afford to provide that. The teachers are very helpful. My academics have improved since joining PiE. In the presence of the teachers, we get to study and practice a lot”.

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PiE programme is a multi-dimensional educative project that is designed for the benefit of students. The benefits from the PiE are not limited alone to traditional education. Along with the academic, the benefits are more socio-psychological in nature, which directly contributes to the student's progress. About this, respondent 5 states;

“Children get benefited in their academics directly, the help they don't receive from the school they do in PiE. They also learn to socialize, about social norms and values, ECAs. Being a PiE student is a privilege in itself, hence students are being benefited on many levels”.

Similarly, respondent 1 supports the view of students benefiting from the PiE programme by mentioning;

“PiE students don't have to pay for classes, even the volunteers and the trainees don't take charge, it's all selfless, there's no payment for anyone. They come voluntarily to make a small impact on the lives of children. Students are not forced, most come to study and for assistance in academics, some might attend schools because of family pressure but they come to PiE because of their interests and for fulfilling their needs. There is no compulsion”.

While students' benefits are concerned, respondent 7 adds to support the view by saying;

“Underprivileged children don't have the opportunity to learn regarding academics and other things. Society cannot take care of such children but we can through PiE, our program is raising our society's children”.

Similarly, respondent 8 replies to support the academic support students receive and benefits from PiE and enhances the academic progress through educative activities by stating;

“I believe that most of the students who join the PiE program benefit a lot in their lives. Social responsibility would mean that eventually they also come to know that they can also make a difference in the lives of others. From the trainees' and volunteers' side, there is a social obligation because they sacrifice their sleep and study time. Many of them come because they like to, not out of compulsion therefore it is highly socially responsible in that way”.

About the academic growth and development of the student through the PiE programme, there are a few outstanding examples that PiE has contributed to enhancing the student's academic progress and educative learning. These few outstanding performances can reflect as an example that illustrates the effectiveness of the PiE programme. This has brought about changes in students' lives, which would have been difficult for underprivileged students to achieve. In this relation, respondent 6 says;

“There are a lot of examples that concern not only the academic performance but also the extra-curricular achievements of the students. I would like to give an example of a former student of PiE from class 10 who was probably one of the best students we ever had, he was a very curious guy who used to ask a lot of questions in class. In SEE, he scored a 3.75 GPA which was the

greatest achievement for him as well as PiE, in addition to that he was able to pass the entrance exam of St. Xavier's College. This is probably one of the most remarkable things that happened in PiE to date”.

Partnership in education has become an effective means for academic growth and development in students. Although practicing partnerships in education is limited to nationwide projects, however, most colleges in Nepal have associated with international collaboration also. This further enables to mitigate the international perspectives in a national and local area to raise the standard of locally deprived students through enhancement of quality in education

Social responsibility toward enhancing the quality of educational lives

Every organization is socially bound towards society. Moreover, social responsibility towards the favour of increasing educational lives has become an important aspect in developing nations like Nepal. This is because most students who become a part of PiE belong to the deprived community. The nationwide initiative towards the PiE programme can enable the deprived community to enhance their academic realm by receiving a quality education. This directly contributes through offering quality to increase educational lives, which further contributes to the rise of human capital in the country.

While educational lives are a concern, it is closely related to bringing about changes in behaviour, shaping the required personality, and increasing knowledge and ability to solve existing problems. Becoming socially responsible to enhance the quality of education is essential, which can come from an academic organization/institute. Respondent 8 states his views to support the quality of education through becoming socially responsible by mentioning;

“The trainees and volunteers get a chance to extend and share what they have learned in their classes and conferences at college through PiE classes to these children who don't have such foundations. We have strict rules and regulations for the PiE children, punctuality, proper behaviour, and respecting others are very important, we have also started value education classes these days, and we have conferences and counseling services. Because of these, the PiE students come to know about good values and then promote social well-being”.

In response to support the view respondent 6 mentions;

“PiE is socially responsible for bringing a change because the students are learning not only about academics but also life skills through various programs conducted by us which include leadership sessions, motivational classes, and so on. Hence, PiE has established such a platform where students get to learn and explore out of the box. This has also brought a positive change in them. How they come in the beginning and how they end up becoming at the end is the best part. Therefore, I do believe that PiE is socially responsible towards the students”.

Further elaborating on her views, respondent 6 states;

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“PiE is established under the supervision of St. Xavier’s College. The volunteers come from +2 and A levels while the trainees come from the BSW Department of the college. They possess the norms and values of the college which they are trying to pass down to the students of PiE. This has helped to teach the students about punctuality, politeness, language, etc. Hence, in this way, PiE is acting as an institution just like St. Xavier’s College”.

Major responsibilities when it comes to the enhancement of students’ standards are contributed by the host organization that is providing the Partnership in education. This is because PiE students who come to receive the education come from a deprived community society. It can be difficult for these students to acquire the quality of education from the government or public schools. This is also because of the reason that government schools and public schools are reluctant to provide additional facilities for the students at schools. One of the reasons why the government and public schools fail to offer these qualities in education is that the government is not taking the initiative to enhance the quality standard of government-owned schools. Most privately owned schools, colleges, and universities charge high education fees and can easily have the capacity to invest in extra-curricular activities to enable the quality and enhance the educational lives of the students.

Although government and public schools are funded by the local government the investment in extracurricular activities is limited offered. On the other hand, almost all government and public schools have low fee structures and have less capability for additional investment in quality education. However, these government and public schools heavily rely on government funding and serve the poor community students, which is also necessary to spread education to all. Moreover, criticizing the government and public schools is rhetoric and nevertheless, it is evident that the Nepalese government have widely spread its wing in education in different rural part of the country which so far is contributing to education for all. Moreover, the social responsibility of the government cannot be ignored. However, when quality is concerned with enhancing educational lives, it can be possible in the hands of privately owned institutes. However, replicating the PiE programme by a privately owned organization/institute to earn a profit is not considered as becoming socially responsible towards the community.

While two aspects of academic progress are being discussed, education and educational lives differ from one another. Education is a basic formal education that is delivered by any educational organization/institute, on the other hand, educational lives is an added value for the students through the assimilation of extra-curricular and social, psychological, and physiological aspects of learning that enables them to change their behaviour, personality and acquire a modern method of teaching and learning. Respondent 7 indicates this by saying;

“We give them value education classes where we select some videos to present. We try to teach them many things. If children are changing then that’s bringing a change in society. If we can change a person, we can change a society”.

In response to possible lucrative endeavors through PiE due to the possibility of receiving grants and funds in the name of PiE and offering quality education to enrich educational lives, some privately owned organizations/institutes can initiate these kinds of programme to win over the societal expenses. This is illustrated by respondent 7 who he states that;

“I feel like other institutions might take a program like PiE as a business. Our program is completely selfless hence it’s different”.

Moreover, the initiative of becoming socially responsible and enabling added value to students, trainees, and volunteers involved with PiE has enhanced the quality of educational lives of all within the PiE programme. The design of PiE is to serve and to lead based on providing both education and enhancing the quality of educational lives to all involved. The serve and lead initiatives have benefited the students but also have additionally contributed to benefit the trainees and volunteers of PiE. In this relation, respondent 1 states;

“Every Friday, we conduct Value Education Classes and in the Value Education Classes, we teach them about several topics. PiE is a child caring center that inspires both our trainees and volunteers, where they get to practice everything, they had learned during their school days. Volunteers express that they get a different feeling when they come for PiE. In addition to that, many volunteers have confessed that they learned to talk to large groups and in front of huge masses after joining PiE”.

In supporting respondent, 1 view, respondent 5 adds;

“PiE runs as an organization where everything about the values, morals, and social responsibility are taught and followed. Students’ values are to come to PiE on time, learn, and live in conjunction, trainees’ values are different, and they have to follow college rules and norms. Volunteers are very dedicated and they too have to follow certain rules and have different responsibilities”.

In the same line, respondent 5 admits the PiE programme is solely concerned with becoming socially responsible towards the community and has added value in educational lives and educational academic progress, he adds by saying;

“PiE is socially responsible for bringing a change because we have been able to bring a change in some students’ lives. The PiE students often pass the entrance exams of reputed colleges after completing PiE classes. We teach about good values and norms in PiE which somehow guides the trainees, volunteers, and the students. Hence, PiE is responsible in the society”.

While discussing further education and educational lives, the end benefit is received by the students who are PiE participants. An organization/institute collaborating with an international organization to initiate PiE claims that educational lives have been transformed. However, the outcome of the PiE programme is

evaluated by the students who eventually benefit from the PiE. About this, respondent 4 (students) answers the real outcome of PiE by stating that;

“Once, during St. Xavier’s day, Father presented a very meaningful video and it completely changed me, I believe it might have impacted others as well, 50% of students would surely have a positive impact through such videos. As people say “Until you get wounded you won’t know” when we get to see such videos directly it makes us feel motivated and driven as we realize the lessons imparted through the video”.

Another respondent 3 (student) supported this by stating;

“TV is one of the devices being used in PiE classes and we also have a computer lab. Our schools also have the devices but we don’t get to use them. Senior students of classes 9 and 10 use a projector but we don’t even get to use the computer lab. We don’t have presentations in school. We learn and remember better through visual presentations and videos hence the teachers in PiE present videos on course-related content, history, and so on in the class. The things we don’t learn in school are taught here like we learn about the happenings around other countries. It does not create distractions as the teachers present videos according to the scheduled time. Every Friday and sometimes between the other classes we learn through TV. It possesses no negative impacts on us”.

Similarly, respondent 2 adds by stating the enhancement of quality in educational lives;

“We get to learn about games we had never played before hence it also aids in enhancing our knowledge. I have always liked basketball but didn’t get to play very often before, I did have a coach, I once asked Father Principal if I could join the basketball classes held in college and he agreed. I practiced and learned a lot about basketball. We have academic classes for 5 days per week and on Fridays, we play games voluntarily. No, it does not create hindrances in academics because we study hard during those 5 days of the week when we have classes and the games are just for refreshment. We understand that we have to prioritize studies as well hence we usually study and play sometimes”.

Towards the expansion of becoming socially responsible through becoming accountable equally, all actors in PiE have their roles, and tasks to perform. Within the St. Xavier’s College, PiE programme, accountability is an important factor, which everyone fulfills in their responsible ways. In connection to this, respondent 4 (student) mentions his views by stating;

“In the other tuition classes, a particular student comes who learns a particular subject for a certain period and leaves however PiE teachers look over everything including the background and status of the students which makes it very different from the other regular classes. They conduct an interview session and only those who pass are admitted here, these criteria are a must because those who want to learn must only be admitted. There must be a genuine willingness to study in those who join PiE because the uninterested ones might create disturbances for others. We have art and value education

classes including others. Once when I was personally going through a tough time because of family problems, sister, the counselor of PiE, came to talk to me and it made me feel better”.

Nevertheless, socio-civic responsibility is necessary to activate within the students’ group to further enhance the quality of educational lives. Education and educational lives are important for the growth of young minds. Traditional methods of teaching and learning can achieve academic enhancement but a modern method of teaching promotes enrichment in students. This can be achieved by enhancing the quality of educational lives in educational settings.

Conclusion

Social responsibilities in education are essential for educational transformation. This educational transformation is necessary for students belonging to deprived communities. This is because most deprived community students go to government/public schools that render limited educational activities due to the lack of autonomy in educational management offered by the government. In such cases to promote the educational realm of these students, private institutes/organizations can offer better services by partnering in education. One of the organizations engaged in a partnership in Education (PiE) is St. Xavier’s College. This has enabled students from deprived communities to access educational activities with the modern educational system including technology and digitalization in education. Private institutes engaged with PiE are also able to offer additional extracurricular activities for example, sports, life-skills development, work with digitalized platforms, etc. Moreover, the social responsibility towards transformation through PiE enhances the educational lives of the students who participate in the PiE programme. The study found that transformation through educational partnering is beneficial for students. The PiE programme enhances the academic growth and development of students through various extra-curricular activities and introduces advanced technological teaching and learning platforms and quality education. Social responsibilities in education through the PiE programme enriched the students’ educational lives by teaching value education.

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SXC Journal of Management and Social Sciences (SJMS)

Published by St. Xavier’s College, Maitighar, Kathmandu, Nepal

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